

Datasheet for the Delpher Newspaper Collection

Title

Delpher Newspaper Collection

Description

The Delpher Newspaper Collection comprises over 2,2 million newspapers, originally printed between 1618 and 2005, and digitised (scanned, Optical Character Recognition, and Optical Lay-out Recognition) between 2006 and the present day. The collection contributes to the overarching goal of the KB, the National Library of the Netherlands, to make large portions of the national print heritage (books, newspapers, and magazines) accessible to the public via the web and available for Text and Data Mining (TDM) for researchers. The collection continues to grow every year.

The newspapers mainly feature general news from the 17th through the 20th centuries, covering a wide range of topics. They include different genres of articles, illustrations, and advertisements, not all of which were customary in every period.

The first segment of the collection, approximately 9 million pages, was digitised between 2006 and 2012 as part of the national programme Large-Scale Research Infrastructure, funded by the Dutch Research Council (NWO), in the digitisation project Databank Digitale Dagbladen (DDD). The newspapers, sourced partly from microfilm and partly from physical copies, were digitised by the German company CCS (Content Conversion Systems) and its Dutch subcontractor M&R in Kampen, following a European tendering procedure.

As part of the Erfgoed van de Oorlog programme (2008–2010), carried out in collaboration with the NIOD Institute for War, Holocaust and Genocide Studies, nearly all surviving Dutch newspapers from the Second World War were digitised. In total, approximately 200,000 pages from 1,200 wartime newspapers were digitised, including resistance newspapers as well as legal and Nazi newspapers.

From 2011 onward, the collection was further expanded with funding from Metamorfoze, the national programme for the preservation of the Netherlands' paper-based heritage. With this, a second objective was added to the project: ensuring the long-term preservation of newspapers by means of digitisation.

The digitised materials, including images, machine-readable text and associated metadata, have been made available online via freely accessible search interfaces, since 2013 at [delpher.nl](https://www.delpher.nl). Since 2012, the collection has also been offered as data, for TDM purposes. Access is provided via a Java implementation of the Search/Retrieve via URL (SRU) protocol, and metadata, text, and images can be harvested through the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). Upon request, licenses may be granted to access potentially copyright-protected materials for non-commercial research purposes. Access and use are subject to applicable data protection regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Homepage

<https://www.delpher.nl/nl/kranten>

Publisher

The KB, the National Library of the Netherlands

Dataset Curators

The core principles guiding the selection (see 'Initial Data Collection') were defined by an advisory committee consisting of Dutch scholars, librarians, and a journalist. Listed in alphabetical order: Drs. Jan Bos, Prof. Dr. Marcel Broersma, Prof. Dr. Joan Hemels, Prof. Dr. Paul Hoftijzer, Dr. Ewoud Sanders, Dr. Angelie Sens, and Prof. Dr. Frank van Vree (chair).

Current curator: Steven Claeysens

Other Contributors

Over the years, dozens of people have contributed to the digitisation and publication of the newspaper collection, including staff at the KB, other heritage institutions, and the companies carrying out the digitisation work.

Point of Contact

General point of contact: dataservices@kb.nl

Steven Claeysens, Curator of Digital Collections (orcid.org/0000-0003-1110-5935; steven.claeysens@kb.nl)

Papers and/or Other References

Beals, M. H. and Emily Bell, with contributions by Ryan Cordell, Paul Fyfe, Isabel Galina Russell, Tessa Hauswedell, Clemens Neudecker, Julianne Nyhan, Sebastian Padó, Miriam Peña Pimentel, Mila Oiva, Lara Rose, Hannu Salmi, Melissa Terras, and Lorella Viola. "Delpher." The Atlas of Digitised Newspapers and Metadata: Reports from Oceanic Exchanges. Loughborough: 2020. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.11560059>

Claeysens, Steven, 'Nederlandse kranten in Delpher. Een inleiding.' Vlaamse stam. Tijdschrift voor familiegeschiedenis 61 (2) 2025, 127–31. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15600032>

Supported Tasks and Shared Tasks

The dataset is well-suited for applications such as Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Text and Data Mining (TDM). It also includes illustrations, which present opportunities for image analysis and computer vision.

It is important to note that the quality of the full texts is limited due to OCR errors. Moreover, the historical nature of the materials means that significant linguistic and spelling shifts have occurred since their original publication. As a result, the texts may not always align with modern language and spelling conventions, which can complicate contemporary analysis and applications. At the same time, they have proven valuable for a wide range of historical research.

AI Category

[Natural Language Processing](#), [Computer Vision](#), [Machine Learning](#)

Type of Cultural Heritage Application

[Metadata Enrichment](#)

(Cultural Heritage) Application Example

Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG)

Distribution

Data Access URL

Available only to authorised users

Licensing Information

Newspapers originally published more than 140 years ago are assumed to no longer be protected by copyright or other intellectual property rights and are considered part of the public domain, and as such the various associated files are free to use by anyone for any purpose, conforming to the [Creative Commons Public Domain Mark](#).

Newspapers published in more recent periods may still be protected by intellectual property rights. Consequently, texts and illustrations may be subject to copyright or have an unclear legal status. Copyright for different components of a newspaper, such as articles, illustrations, or photographs, can expire at different times. Under Dutch copyright law this partly depends on whether the rights are initially held by the publisher (as employer) or by the individual creator. Copyright lasts for 70 years after the death of the author, illustrator, photographer, or other contributor; where the copyright is held by the publisher, it expires on 1 January of the 71st year after publication.

Dutch newspapers may also be protected by the European database right. It lasts for 15 years after publication and protects publishers against reuse (copying and/or republishing) of a whole newspaper issue or a substantial part of it.

The KB makes every effort to secure licences with publishers (or their legal successors) and collective management organisations (CMOs) for titles that are not in the public domain, enabling publication on Delpher and the provision of data for non-commercial academic research.

The metadata is made available under the [Creative Commons CC0 Public Domain Dedication](#).

File Format

- bitonal Searchable Image PDF file at the issue level;
- JPEG-2000 master images, mostly in greyscale, at the page level [archived, not published];
- JPEG-2000 access images, mostly in colour, at the page level;
- ALTO files, with layout and text at the page level;
- plain text in XML, segmented at the article level;
- MPEG21-DIDL file for every issue. This file includes descriptive metadata (in Dublin Core) and structural metadata about the relationship between the individual files.

Citation Information

Delpher krantencollectie, KB, Nationale Bibliotheek van Nederland, Den Haag. Verkregen op YYYY-MM-DD.

Delpher Newspaper Collection, KB, National Library of the Netherlands, The Hague. Retrieved on YYYY-MM-DD.

Next to this, each newspaper title, each newspaper page, and each newspaper article has a persistent URL that resolves to Delpher. For example, illustrated here by the oldest Dutch newspaper: <https://resolver.kb.nl/resolve?urn=ddd:010500649>, the first page: <https://resolver.kb.nl/resolve?urn=ddd:010500649:mpeg21:p001>, and the first article <https://resolver.kb.nl/resolve?urn=ddd:010500649:mpeg21:a0001>.

Composition

The dataset comprises over 2.2 million historical newspapers, originally printed between 1618 and 2005 and digitised using scanning, optical character recognition, and optical layout recognition. The data includes images, machine-readable text, and associated metadata.

Dataset Category

Content and metadata

Media Category

Image and text

Object Type

Newspaper

Dataset Structure

The metadata records consist of two types of metadata.

1. Structural metadata in MPEG21-DIDL format. These metadata describe the hierarchical structure of the newspaper issue: issue, pages and articles. These metadata are listed within the <didl:DIDL> element.
2. Descriptive metadata in Dublin Core format and extensions of this format. These metadata are listed within the <srw_dc:dcx> elements, which are embedded in the <didl:DIDL> element. There are descriptive metadata on several levels: the issue, each page and each article.

For schemas, see ‘Compliance with Standard(s)’.

The MPEG21-DIDL consists of:

- the hierarchy of the newspaper issue: each issue has 1-n pages and 1-n articles
- identifiers of the newspaper and all its parts
- the descriptive metadata of the issue, the pages and the articles

- zoning information with coordinates describing the location of the article on the image of the page
- URLs to all the files that are part of the newspaper issue
- checksums of the files that are part of the newspaper issue

The structure of a newspaper issue is described by three elements:

- Items
- Components
- Resources

The structure of the newspaper is described by the hierarchical nesting of Item elements. A root Item element is used for the newspaper issue. Nested within this Item, each page and each article is described by a (sub)Item.

There is an n-to-n relationship between pages and articles. A page can have several articles, and an article can be printed on several pages. For this reason the Items for articles are not nested in the page-Items, but are on the same hierarchical level.

A page-Item does have one or more sub-Items which describe the article parts that are printed on the page.

Example: a two-page newspaper issue with three articles. The second article starts on page 1 and continues on page 2. This newspaper issue is described by an Item for the entire newspaper issue. This Item has five sub-Items (two for the pages and three for the articles). Page 1 has two article-parts, one for the entire first article and one for the start of the second article. Page 2 has two article-parts, one for the continuation of the second article and one for the third article.

```

ITEM (newspaper issue)
  ITEM (page 1)
    ITEM (article-part, i.e. the entire article 1)
    ITEM (article-part, i.e. the first part of article 2)
  ITEM (page 2)
    ITEM (article-part, i.e. the second part of article 2)
    ITEM (article-part, i.e. the entire article 3)
  ITEM (article 1)
  ITEM (article 2)
  ITEM (article 3)

```

Each Item contains Components, which represent all the available components of the Item.

The newspaper issue Item consists of two Components: one Component describing the PDF file of the complete issue, and a second Component containing the descriptive metadata of the issue.

The Items representing pages have five Components, plus sub-Items for the article parts of the page: four Components describing the available file types for the page (master image, access image, ALTO file, and technical metadata), one Component containing the descriptive metadata of the page, and one sub-Item for each article part on the page.

The Items representing articles have three Components: one Component containing the zoning information, which lists the coordinates of the article part on the page (used for highlighting the article part on the page image), one Component containing the descriptive metadata of the article, and a third Component representing the full-text file of the article.

The general layout of the MPEG21-DIDL is:

```

ITEM (newspaper issue)
  COMPONENT (descriptive metadata newspaper issue)
  COMPONENT (PDF)
  ITEM (page 1)
    COMPONENT (descriptive metadata page 1)
    COMPONENT (master image page 1)
    COMPONENT (XML technical metadata page)

```

COMPONENT (access image page 1)
 COMPONENT (XML ALTO page 1)
 ITEM (article-part 1)
 COMPONENT (descriptive metadata article)
 COMPONENT (zoning-information article-part 1)
 ITEM (article-part 2)
 COMPONENT (descriptive metadata article)
 COMPONENT (zoning-information article-part 2)
 ITEM (page 2)

 etc. for each page
 ITEM (article 1)
 COMPONENT (descriptive metadata article 1)
 COMPONENT (articletext article 1)
 COMPONENT (zoning-information article 1)
 ITEM (article 2)

 etc. for each article

Each Component can have a nested Resource element. Resources represent the physical files that make up the newspaper issue. These are referred to by

1. a URL (e.g. a URL to an image, an XMLfile or a PDF file). These are persistent URLs to the files. They are listed in the ref-attribute of the Resource element. In these cases there is an extra <dcx :md5_checksum> attribute, listing the checksum of the file.
2. or the data can be inline within the MPEG21-DIDL (e.g. descriptive metadata). They are contained in the <srw_dc :dcx> elements.

Each Item and each Component has a unique identifier, listed in the dc:identifier attribute.

The identifiers reflect the hierarchical structure of the newspaper issue.

Identifier type	Example
Newspaper issue	ddd:010246000:mpeg21
Descriptive metadata of the newspaper issue	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:metadata
PDF file	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:pdf
Page	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:p001
Descriptive metadata of the page	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:p001:metadata
Master image	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:p001:image/preservation
Technical metadata of the master image	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:p001:metadata/technical
Access image	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:p001:image

ALTO file	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:p001:alto
Article-part	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:p001:a0001
Descriptive metadata of article-part	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:p001:a0001:metadata
Zoning information of article-part	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:p001:a0001:zoning
Article	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:a0035
Text file of article	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:a0035:ocr
Descriptive metadata of article	ddd:010246000:mpeg21:a0035:metadata

Please note the difference between identifiers referring to articles and to article-parts.

Each Item and each Component has a Descriptor which describes the role of the element in the newspaper issue. The roles are listed in the Statement element of the Descriptor.

Role	Comment
metadata	Descriptive metadata. This role is used on several levels: entire newspaper issue, page and article level.
PDF	PDF files contain the entire newspaper issue
page x	
article x	
image/preservation	master image
metadata/technical	technical metadata of the master image (mix format)
image	access image
alto	layout and text of a page

ocr	fulltext file of an article
metadata/zoning	zoning information This role is used on two levels: article and article-part level

Zoning information describes the blocks on a page (text blocks or graphical elements).

It contains:

- A reference to the page image file.
- The coordinates of each block on the image (which can be used to highlight the block on the image).
- A reference to the ALTO file of the page and to the TextBlocks within the ALTO file.
- The ordering of blocks to define the reading order.

The zoning information is listed at two levels in the MPEG21-DIDL:

1. The article parts contain zoning information with the coordinates of each block (area) of the article part, expressed in `<dcx:coordinates>`.
2. The articles list the zoning information for all parts of the article. At this level, the coordinates are listed again in `<dcx:coordinates>`, and an additional element, `<dcx:blocks>`, lists the blocks in the ALTO file. Please note that the ALTO file contains much more detailed information on the page layout.

Data Instances

Not applicable

Data Fields

Descriptive metadata is available at three levels.

1. Descriptive metadata at the newspaper **issue** level

Element	Comment
<code><dc:title></code>	Title of the newspaper
<code><dcterms:alternative></code>	Alternative title. This can take one of two forms: the value starts with "Ook bekend onder de naam" ("also known as"), or the value starts with "Eerder verschenen onder de naam" ("previously published as").
<code><dcterms:isVersionOf></code>	Alternative title of the newspaper. This corresponds to "Ook bekend onder de naam" (see <code><dcterms:alternative></code>), but in this case only

	the alternative newspaper title is listed, without the leading text.
<dc:identifier xsi:type="dcx:PPN">	PPN of the newspaper title. This is the identifier of the title in the national catalogue GGC.
<dc:date>	Date of publication of the newspaper issue
<dcterms:temporal>	Edition of the newspaper issue. This can be: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ochtend (morning edition) - Middag (afternoon edition) - Avond (evening edition) - Dag (single-day edition)
<dc:rights>	The copyright holder of the newspaper title
<dcx:recordRights>	The KB (which is not the rights holder)
<dc:publisher>	Publisher of the newspaper title
<dcterms:spatial>	Geographical area. This can be: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Landelijk (national newspaper title) - Regionaal/lokaal (regional or local newspaper title) - Nederlandse Antillen - Suriname - Nederlands-Indië / Indonesië
<dc:source>	Institution that holds the original newspaper, shelfmark
<dcx:volume>	The volume within the newspaper title (as printed on the original)
<dcx:issuenummer>	The number within the newspaper title (as printed on the original).
<dcx:recordIdentifier>	The identifier of the digital newspaper issue

<dc:identifier>	The URL to the MPEG21-DIDL file which describes the newspaper issue
<dc:type xsi:type="dcterms:DCMIType">	The document type (value is always Text)
<dc:language xsi:type="dcterms:IS0639-1">	The main language of the newspaper issue
<dcterms:isPartOf xsi:type="dcx:collectionIdentifier">	The identifier of the digital collection
<dcterms:isPartOf>	The description of the digital collection
<dcterms:issued>	The publication years of the newspaper title
<ddd:yearsDigitized>	The publication years of the newspaper title that are have been digitised and are part of the Delpher Newspaper Collection
<dcterms:spatial xsi:type="dcx:creation">	The place of publication of the newspaper title

2. Descriptive metadata on the **page** level

Element	Comment
<ddd:nativePageNumber>	The page number as printed on the original page
<dcx:recordIdentifier>	The identifier of the digital page
<dc:identifier>	The persistent URL to the page (redirected to the Delpher landing page)
<dc:type xsi:type="dcterms:DCMIType">	The document type (value is always Text)

<ddd:OCRConfidencelevel>	Confidence level of the correctness of the character recognition on this page, 0 is no confidence at all, 1 is highest confidence. (This page confidence level is an aggregate of the confidence levels for each word and character, as listed in the ALTO files).
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3. Descriptive metadata on the **article** level

Element	Comment
<dc:subject>	The type of article. This can be one of four values: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Familiebericht (family notice) - Advertentie (advertisement or small notice) - Illustratie met onderschrift (illustration with caption, not part of an article) - Artikel (regular article)
<dc:title>	The article heading (please note that dc:title is also used on the issue level, where it designates the newspaper title).
<dcterms:accessRights>	PLEASE IGNORE. This is not a rights statement.
<dc:identifier>	The persistent URL to the article (redirected to the Delpher landing page)
<dc:type xsi:type="dcterms:DCMIType">	The document type (value is always Text)

Compliance with Standard(s)

<https://www.w3.org/TR/xml/>

<https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/>

<https://www.loc.gov/standards/alto/>

<https://mpeg.chiariglione.org/standards/mpeg-21/digital-item-declaration.html>

<https://jpeg.org/jpeg2000/>

Data Splits

Not applicable

Language

The content is primarily in Dutch. The dataset includes small amounts of content in French, Latin, English, German, Frisian, Papiamentu, German, and Sranan Tongo.

nld, fra, lat, eng, fry, pap, deu, srn ([ISO 639-2](#))

Descriptive Statistics

Not available

Data Collection Process

The original paper items are preserved by the KB, supplemented with items from several dozen national and international heritage organisations.

There are no comparable collections of digitised Dutch newspapers matching this one in number or scope.

Curation Rationale

In the initial project phase (the DDD project), priority was given to enabling online digital access, with a primary focus on supporting scholarly research. Subsequently, the project objectives were expanded to include facilitating wider public access, including use for non-scholarly purposes, as well as providing access for text and data mining (TDM).

In the second phase, which was financed through the Metamorfoze programme, an additional objective was introduced: to ensure the long-term preservation of newspaper collections through systematic digitisation.

At present, the project continues to regard access as its principal objective, while digital preservation is maintained as a secondary, complementary goal.

Source Data

The source data consist of printed newspapers, or microfilms thereof, that have survived and are, in principle, preserved in a publicly accessible collection.

Initial Data Collection

The newspapers were selected from the holdings of numerous archives and libraries, mostly in the Netherlands. What has been digitised is therefore partly dependent on centuries of preservation policies of the collective public institutions, in the Netherlands and abroad. Newspapers that have not survived can not be digitised.

The collection was compiled by a committee of academic researchers and KB staff. The advisory committee developed a working definition of a newspaper: a publication produced by a printing press in multiple identical copies, issued at a fixed periodicity on a specified day, containing a

substantial volume of content relating to current affairs of all types, and made available for purchase by the general public. The committee delineated distinct time periods in the history of the Dutch press and established separate categories for the various former Dutch colonies. For each time period and category, the available titles were evaluated with regard to their societal representativeness at the time of publication. Additional criteria included scholarly research value, geographical representation, chronological distribution, and political and denominational diversity. The primary objective was to create a comprehensive and representative collection of historical newspapers from the pre-digital era.

The collection contains most national newspapers, together with a selection of regional and local newspapers, newspapers from former Dutch colonies, and a small number of U.S.-based newspapers from the Dutch diaspora. Nearly all Dutch newspapers from the Second World War were digitised, while newspapers already digitised elsewhere, as well as those in a condition too poor to digitise, were excluded.

For publications from the 17th and 18th centuries, completeness was pursued to the extent permitted by the surviving material. From the 19th century onwards, a representative selection approach was adopted.

Source Data Producers

The texts included in the dataset were created mainly by Dutch writers who could be considered professional, reflecting the historical reality that the majority of such writers were, for a long time, predominantly men. The same applies to the various illustrations and their creators. For the earliest centuries, however, the term “professional” is to some extent an anachronism in this context.

Digitisation Pipeline

A dedicated team of librarians at the KB identifies surviving copies of the selected newspapers, arranges loan agreements with the holding institutions, and prepares the newspapers for transportation and digitisation by specialised companies. Each newspaper issue is meticulously assessed for completeness and digitisation feasibility. The newspapers are scanned and processed with optical character recognition (OCR) and optical layout recognition (OLR) by digitisation firms in accordance with strict guidelines.

The precise technologies and workflows used in the digitisation process are not disclosed by the digitisation companies. It is known, however, that all newspapers are digitised using ABBYY software, version 7.0 or later, and that headlines are manually corrected. The results are subsequently subjected to semi-automated quality control by KB staff.

This information is included in the ALTO file as follows (example):

```
<preProcessingStep>
  - <processingDateTime>2009-12-11</processingDateTime>
  <processingAgency>
    CCS Content Conversion Specialists GmbH, www.content-conversion.com
  </processingAgency>
  <processingStepDescription>align</processingStepDescription>
  - <processingStepSettings>CCS OCR Processing Filter</processingStepSettings>
  <processingSoftware>
    <softwareCreator>CCS Content Conversion Specialists GmbH, Germany</softwareCreator>
    <softwareName>CCS docWORKS</softwareName>
    <softwareVersion>6.3-0.96</softwareVersion>
    <applicationDescription/>
  </processingSoftware>
</preProcessingStep>
<ocrProcessingStep>
```

```
- <processingSoftware>
  <softwareCreator>ABBYY (BIT Software), Russia</softwareCreator>
  <softwareName>FineReader</softwareName>
  <softwareVersion>8.1</softwareVersion>
</processingSoftware>
</ocrProcessingStep>
```

Preprocessing and Cleaning

Not applicable

Annotations

Not applicable

Annotation Process

Not applicable

Annotators

Not applicable

Crowd Labour

Guided by Prof. Dr. Nicoline van der Sijs (Meertens Institute), a group of skilled volunteers manually re-keyed a substantial part of the 17th-century newspapers. These newspapers have also been published as part of the Couranten Corpus by the Dutch Language Institute, with additional metadata, including part-of-speech tagging (cf. <https://ivdnt.org/corpora-lexica/courantencorpus/>)

Where applicable, the ALTO files include the post-processing information listed below (example taken from the file referenced above in the “Digitisation Pipeline” section).

```
<postProcessingStep>
  <processingDateTime>2015-04-24T15:16:01</processingDateTime>
  <processingAgency>Meertens Instituut</processingAgency>
  <processingStepDescription>Manual correction ocr</processingStepDescription>
  - <processingSoftware>
    <softwareCreator>Meertens Instituut</softwareCreator>
    - <softwareName>
      nl.knaw.meertens.crowdsourcing.kb.AltoArticleAligner
    </softwareName>
    <softwareVersion/>
  </processingSoftware>
</postProcessingStep>
```

The original OCR files are available upon request.

Data Provenance

Not applicable

Use of Linked Open Data, Controlled Vocabularies, Multilingual Ontologies/Taxonomies

Not applicable

Version Information

The collection is updated at irregular intervals. The most recent release dates from 3 December 2024.

Release Date

Not applicable

Date of Modification

Not applicable

Checksums

Not applicable at the dataset level, but the MPEG21-DIDL files include checksums for all files associated with a single newspaper issue.

Maintenance plan

Maintenance level

Actively Maintained

Update Periodicity

Irregular

Examples and Considerations for Using the Data

Ethical Considerations

Personal and Other Sensitive Information

The newspapers include extensive personal information concerning public figures (e.g., politicians and sportspeople) as well as 'ordinary' citizens, particularly through genres such as family notices, advertisements, judicial reports, records of manumission, passenger lists, etc. No efforts were made to anonymise these data.

Under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR/AVG), personal data relating to individuals who are still alive must be processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently. Those accessing or processing the dataset are responsible for ensuring compliance with the GDPR, as this dataset contains personally identifiable information (PII) protected by personality rights.

Discussion of Biases

For centuries, both the authorship and the target audience of newspapers were largely male.

Perspectives on issues such as slavery, the position of women in society, people of colour, and other marginalised groups in 17th-, 18th-, and 19th-century newspapers have changed considerably. Texts that are now recognised as highly harmful - including misogynistic, racist, antisemitic, and similar views - were, by and large, considered normal at the time. Twentieth-century newspapers also contain biased views, including strongly ideological perspectives, such as those presented in National Socialist newspapers published in the period leading up to and during the Second World War.

A section of the newspapers was published in the former Dutch colonies, mostly representing the views of the colonisers.

Potential Societal Impact of Using the Dataset

The newspapers provide a comprehensive overview of the dominant public discourse(s) in the Netherlands. As such, they offer an explicitly historical, rather than contemporary, perspective on Dutch language, culture, and society. This historical lens enables, amongst others, in-depth study of long-term developments in journalistic practices, political communication, societal views, and linguistic change. At the same time, the dataset inevitably reproduces the biases and exclusions inherent in those earlier discourses. This constitutes both the strength and the principal risk of the dataset, and it is in this dual character that the primary potential societal impact of the data resides.

Examples of Datasets, Publications and Models that (re-)use the Dataset

Datasets (selection)

Common Corpus. https://huggingface.co/datasets/PlE1As/common_corpus

Couranten Corpus, Instituut voor de Nederlandse taal.
<https://ivdnt.org/corpora-lexica/courantencorpus/>

Delpher open krantenarchief (1.0). [Creative Commons Naamsvermelding 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), Den Haag, 2019.
<https://www.delpher.nl/over-delpher/delpher-open-krantenarchief> [Public Domain subset of Delpher Newspaper Collection]

Europeana Newspapers. https://huggingface.co/datasets/biglam/europeana_newspapers

van Kasteel, Teun, and Jens Aurich. (2024), *Amok Events in 19th Century Dutch Newspapers*. IISG, Amsterdam. <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/0WWWVT>

Kleppe, M., et al. (2016), *Koninklijke Bibliotheek Kranten – 1 Miljoen (KBK-1M)*. KB Lab: The Hague. <https://doi.org/10.17026/dans-xar-hqvg>

Läuferts, Josephine, and Jens Aurich. (2024), *Desertion Events in 19th Century Dutch Newspapers*. IISG: Amsterdam. <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/D6OXZ9>

Smits, Thomas, and Willem Jan Faber. (2018) *CHRONIC (Classified Historical Newspaper Images)*. KB Lab: The Hague.
<http://lab.kb.nl/dataset/chronic-classified-historical-newspaper-images>

Wevers, Melvin, and Juliette Lonij (2017) *SIAMESET*. KB Lab: The Hague.
<http://lab.kb.nl/dataset/siameset>

Wilms, Lotte, et al. (2020), *Historical newspaper OCR ground-truth data set*. KB Lab: The Hague. <https://lab.kb.nl/dataset/historical-newspapers-ocr-ground-truth>

Publications (selection)

Brate, Ryan, et al. 'Capturing Contentiousness: Constructing the Contentious Terms in Context Corpus'. Proceedings of the 11th on Knowledge Capture Conference [New York, NY, USA], K-CAP '21, 2021, pp. 17–24. ACM Digital Library, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3460210.3493553>.

Broersma, Marcel, and Frank Harbers. 'Exploring Machine Learning to Study the Long-Term Transformation of News: Digital Newspaper Archives, Journalism History, and Algorithmic Transparency'. *Digital Journalism*, vol. 6, no. 9, Oct. 2018, pp. 1150–64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2018.1513337>.

Hengchen, Simon, et al. 'A Data-Driven Approach to Studying Changing Vocabularies in Historical Newspaper Collections'. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, vol. 36, no. Supplement_2, Nov. 2021, pp. ii109–ii126. <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqab032>.

Huijnen, Pim, et al. 'A Digital Humanities Approach to the History of Science'. *Social Informatics*, edited by Akiyo Nadamoto et al., vol. 8359, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2014, pp. 71–85. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-55285-4_6.

Huijnen, Pim. 'Everyday Memory: A Computational Analysis of Changing Relations between Past and Present in Dutch Newspapers in the 20th Century'. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, vol. 40, no. Supplement_1, Jan. 2025, pp. i27–38. <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqad099>.

van Eijnatten, Joris. 'Something about the Weather. Using Digital Methods to Mine Geographical Conceptions of Europe in Twentieth-Century Dutch Newspapers'. *BMGN - Low Countries Historical Review*, vol. 134, no. 1, Mar. 2019, p. 28. <https://doi.org/10.18352/bmgn-ldhr.10655>.

van Eijnatten, Joris, and Pim Huijnen. 'Something Happened to the Future: Reconstructing Temporalities in Dutch Parliamentary Debate, 1814–2018'. *Contributions to the History of Concepts*, vol. 16, no. 2, Dec. 2021, pp. 52–82. <https://doi.org/10.3167/choc.2021.160204>.

van Eijnatten, Joris, and Ruben Ros. 'The Eurocentric Fallacy. A Digital-Historical Approach to the Concepts of "Modernity", "Civilization" and "Europe" (1840–1990)'. *International Journal for History, Culture and Modernity*, vol. 7, no. 1, Nov. 2019, pp. 686–736. <https://doi.org/10.18352/hcm.580>.

van Erp, Marieke, et al. 'More than the Name of the Rose'. *The American Historical Review*, vol. 128, no. 1, Mar. 2023, pp. 335–69. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ahr/rhad141>.

van Erp, Marieke, et al. 'Slicing and Dicing a Newspaper Corpus for Historical Ecology Research'. *Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management*, edited by Catherine Faron Zucker et al., vol. 11313, Springer International Publishing, 2018, pp. 470–84. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-03667-6_30.

Jacobi, Carina, et al. 'Quantitative Analysis of Large Amounts of Journalistic Texts Using Topic Modelling'. *Digital Journalism*, vol. 4, no. 1, Jan. 2016, pp. 89–106. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2015.1093271>.

van Lange, Milan, and Ralf Futselaar. 'Debating Evil'. *Contributions to Contemporary History*, vol. 59, no. 1, June 2019. <https://doi.org/10.51663/pnz.59.1.07>.

Martinez-Ortiz, Carlos, et al. 'Design and Implementation of ShiCo: Visualising Shifting Concepts over Time'. Proceedings of the 3rd HistInformatics Workshop on Computational History, edited by Marten Düring et al., vol. 1632, CEUR, 2016, pp. 11–19. CEUR Workshop Proceedings. CEUR Workshop Proceedings, https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1632/#paper_2.

Peris, Antoine, et al. 'Information Diffusion between Dutch Cities: Revisiting Zipf and Pred Using a Computational Social Science Approach'. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, vol. 85, Jan. 2021, p. 101565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2020.101565>.

Piersoul, Jozefien, et al. '150 years of written Dutch: The construction of the Dutch Corpus of Contemporary and Late Modern Periodicals'. *Nederlandse Taalkunde*, vol. 26, no. 3, Dec. 2021, pp. 339–62. <https://doi.org/10.5117/NEDTAA2021.3.002.PIER>.

Ros, Ruben. 'Conceptualizing an Outside World: The Case of "Foreign" in Dutch Newspapers 1815–1914'. *Contributions to the History of Concepts*, vol. 16, no. 2, Dec. 2021, pp. 27–51. <https://doi.org/10.3167/choc.2021.160203>.

Wevers, Melvin. 'Mining Historical Advertisements in Digitised Newspapers'. *Digitised Newspapers – A New Eldorado for Historians?*, edited by Estelle Bunout et al., De Gruyter, 2022, pp. 227–52. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110729214-011>.

Wevers, Melvin. 'Tracking the Consumption Junction: Temporal Dependencies between Articles and Advertisements in Dutch Newspapers'. *Digital Humanities Quarterly*, vol. 014, no. 2, June 2020. <http://digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/14/2/000445/000445.html>.

Wevers, Melvin. 'Using Word Embeddings to Examine Gender Bias in Dutch Newspapers, 1950–1990'. *Proceedings of the 1st International Workshop on Computational Approaches to Historical Language Change [Florence, Italy], 2019*, pp. 92–97. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/W19-4712>.

Wevers, Melvin, and Thomas Smits. 'The Visual Digital Turn: Using Neural Networks to Study Historical Images'. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, Jan. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqy085>.

Zhu, Jiaqi, et al. 'Tracing Colonial Discourse in Dutch Historical Newspapers'. *Anthology of Computers and the Humanities*, edited by Taylor Arnold et al., vol. 3, 2025, pp. 1311–23. [anthology.ach.org, https://doi.org/10.63744/SwkybkCCvmsj](https://doi.org/10.63744/SwkybkCCvmsj).

Models (selection)

<https://huggingface.co/emanjavacas/GysBERT>

<https://gpt-nl.nl/>

Known Non-Ethical Limitations

The quality is high, given that the texts and illustrations included in the dataset were created by professionals. However, the machine-readable text is the result of OCR processing carried out over a period of nearly 20 years, which has led to varying levels of accuracy.

Spelling in the earliest centuries is inconsistent with modern Dutch conventions, and both vocabulary and style have changed over time.

A final note of caution: the content of newspapers has evolved considerably over time. Many of the typical sections and genres found in present-day newspapers, such as interviews, columns, advertisements, weather reports, and so on, did not yet exist when the first newspapers were published. Journalistic genres, too, have their own historical development.

Unanticipated Uses made of this Dataset

No unanticipated uses of this dataset are currently known.